

Essential Oils: A Promising Remedy against Fungal and Bacterial Human Keratitis.

Anwer S. El-Badry and Sameh S. Ali *

Botany Department, Faculty of Science, Tanta University, 31527, Tanta, Egypt.

*Corresponding author:

Dr.: Sameh Samir Ali

Email: samh_samir@science.tanta.edu.eg

Out of 112 corneal ulcers, which were clinically diagnosed as patients of microbial infections (fungal, bacterial, acanthamoeba and viral), attending the outpatient clinic and inpatient Ophthalmology Department of Tanta University Hospitals within 6 months (April – September, 2014), 43 cases were detected to possess fungal growth, and 46 cases were possessing bacterial infection according to results of microbial cultivation. All fungal and bacterial isolates were tested against the commercially available antimicrobial ophthalmic preparations (ofloxacin, moxifloxacin, gatifloxacin, tobramycin, ciprofloxacin for bacteria, ketoconazole, fluconazole, itraconazole, natamycin and voriconazole for fungi). Out of them 2 fungal isolates were possessing 80% resistance to the tested antifungal agents, and 3 bacterial isolates gave 80% resistance to the tested antibiotics. All the 5 isolates were tested against 15 commercial essential oils (sage, anise, black seed, mustard, wheat germ, marjoram, jojoba, clove, chamomile, ginger, camphor, rosemary, watercress, parsley and gum oils). In case of fungal isolates, chamomile was the most effective oil against *Aspergillus niger*. The highest inhibition zone for bacterial isolate, identified later as *Staphylococcus aureus*, was recorded against rosemary. The antimicrobial action of the selected oils was highly observable and elucidated by TEM of both *A. niger* and *S. aureus* growth elements. Histopathological studies on the cornea of experimental animals revealed that the selected oils could be promisingly used in the treatment of resistant microbial keratitis.

Key words: *Aspergillus niger*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, essential oils, chamomile, rosemary, histopathology, TEM.

Human keratitis is an inflammation of the cornea, the transparent part of the eye covering the iris, and pupil, and has distinct transparency to allow accurate vision, and passage of light. Migration of the inflammatory cells as an immune response into the corneal layers can disrupt the corneal transparency, resulting in corneal opacification, or complete blindness. Severity of keratitis depends on the number of migrating inflammatory cells; and can be classified into different classes of keratitis according to the causative agent (Djalilian, *et al.*, 2001). Human keratitis may have viral, bacterial, acanthamoebal, or fungal origin with infective

behaviour; or may be caused by dry eye, exposure to very bright light (photokeratitis), injury by foreign objects like dust, pollen, makeup, or contact lenses, and vitamin A deficiency, with only histopathological defects, and absence of microbial growth (Holland, and Schwartz, 1999).

Mycotic keratitis is a disease caused by fungal invasion into the corneal stroma. It is an exogenous infection, attacking the injured corneal epithelium, and establishes the fungal growth within the collagen bound lamellae of stromal layer of cornea. Mycotic keratitis is considered to be a resistant corneal ulcer, which possesses aggressive microbial growth, and becomes not responding to conventional treatments for at least one week, or more, and even becomes worse due to continued fungal growth, proteolysis of collagen, and toxification of cornea by drugs, and fungal toxic secretions (Tanure, *et al.*, 2000).

Many diagnosed mycotic keratitis cases possess delayed healing rates, or even have no response to conventional treatments, referring to many factors, such as high fungal toxicity, high fungal growth rate, poor absorption of large molecule antifungal agents into corneal tissues, toxification of corneal cells by prolonged chemotherapy, and resistance of some fungal elements against antifungal action of the available drugs. Topical application of natamycin, miconazole, itraconazole, ketoconazole, and fluconazole was compared for the healing of different *Fusarium* spp., and *Aspergillus* spp. causing keratitis with less effective healing rates (Brooks, *et al.*, 1998); while the addition of cyclodextrin surfactant increased the penetration rate of miconazole, increasing its antifungal activity *in vitro* (Piel, *et al.*, 1999).

The severity of corneal fungal infections depends on the complete destruction of loosen stromal layer by the proliferation of large-sized hyphae of filamentous fungi, or highly populated cells of yeast forms within the non-bound stromal lamellae. This aggressive growth has no observable chemotactic secretions, or antigenic behaviour, leading to a noticeable delaying of the beneficial host immune response, and mechanisms, that may inhibit the fungal growth naturally (Cristol, *et al.*, 1996).

Bacterial keratitis is an infection and inflammation of the cornea that cause pain, reduced vision, light sensitivity and tearing or discharge from the eye that can, in severe cases cause loss of vision (Tang *et al.*, 2009). Bacterial keratitis progresses rapidly and corneal destruction may be complete in 24 - 48 hours with some of the more virulent bacteria (Acharya *et al.*, 2009). The severity of the corneal infection usually depends on the underlying condition of the cornea and the pathogenicity of the infecting bacteria. It may involve the center of the cornea or the peripheral part of the cornea (that portion closest to the sclera) or both. Keratitis may affect one eye or both eyes. Keratitis may be mild, moderate, or severe and may be associated with inflammation of other parts of the eye (Janumala *et al.*, 2010).

Many wide spread fungi with distinct air-borne spore dissemination may act as the major fungal population in several corneal ulcer surveys; which could be confirmed by the isolation of different *Aspergillus* species from about 40% of corneal ulcer cases in north India in a 3 years study (Chander, and Sharma, 2004). Of the bacteria associated with an ulcerative keratitis, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, a Gram negative bacillus, and *Staphylococcus aureus*, a Gram-positive coccus, are the most common bacterial pathogens (Fukuda, 2009 and Jeng *et al.*, 2010). *S. aureus* is well known for its ability to evolve mechanisms of antibiotic resistance, making these infections among the most difficult to treat, and antibiotic resistance has increased since 2000 (Dave *et al.*, 2011). Although the antibiotic resistance of *S. aureus* is well known, what is less well recognized is that the gene transfer mechanisms that created the highly resistant strains can also transfer virulence traits (McAdam *et al.*, 2012).

The proportion of Gram-positive isolates varies between 56% and 83% and the proportion of Gram-negative isolates varies between 17% and 44%. Differences may reflect climate of the country or prevalence of risk factors such as contact lens use, trauma or co-existent ocular disease (Sueke *et al.*, 2013). The ophthalmologist has a number of potential antimicrobials at their disposal to treat bacterial keratitis. When choosing an antimicrobial prior to the results of bacterial culture and sensitivity, the choice of one drug over another may be determined by a variety of factors, for example local bacterial epidemiology, drug cost, and drug toxicity (Sueke *et al.*, 2013).

In the present time, drug resistance in microbes is a very serious problem. Hence, plant origin herbal medicines are considered as safe alternatives of synthetic drugs (Upadhyay *et al.*, 2010). Due to their antimicrobial, insecticidal, antifungal, and antibacterial activities, essential oils have been intensely screened and applied in the fields of pharmacology, medical and clinical microbiology, phytopathology and food preservation (Daferera *et al.*, 2000).

Rosemary, *Rosmarinus officinalis* L. (Labiatae) is an evergreen perennial shrub grown in many parts of the world. It has been reported to possess a number of therapeutic applications in folk medicines in curing or managing of a wide range of diseases. Rosemary has long been recognized as having antioxidant molecules, such as rosmarinic acid, carnosol, rosmaridiphenol and these have found in ethanol-soluble fraction (Bakirel *et al.*, 2008). Chamomile, *Matricaria recutita* L. (Compositae) is a well-known medicinal plant in folk medicine cultivated all over the world. Chamomile essential oil is widely used in pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and food industries. The pharmacological effect of chamomile is mainly connected with its essential oil for its spasmolytic, antimicrobial, and disinfective properties. The biologically active substances in chamomile essential oil are α -bisabolol, bisabolol oxides and chamazulene (Grgesina *et al.*, 1995).

The aim of this study was to determine the effectiveness of some essential oils as a promising alternative remedy against microbial human keratitis resistant to commercial antimicrobial ophthalmic preparations.

Materials and Methods:

Clinical diagnosis of corneal ulcers:

Six months survey was carried out during the period from April to September, 2014. Collected samples were achieved at regular twice a week visits to the Outpatient Clinic, and daily follow up visits for patients admitted to Inpatient Department of Ophthalmology Hospital, Tanta University, Egypt. Samples were collected from patients that were clinically diagnosed to possess different types of corneal ulcers.

Different types of corneal ulcers were clinically diagnosed and distinguished from each other on the basis of some clinical criteria as follows:

i- Viral corneal ulcer:

Viral corneal ulcer is an infective keratitis caused by Herpes virus, causing the following signs:

Multiple, scattered, thin branched, micro dendritic ulcers with swollen epithelium, stromal edema, infiltration, and vascularization (Shuster, *et al.*, 1988).

ii- Acanthamoebal corneal ulcer:

Acanthamoeba keratitis is characterized by severe pain, decreased vision, redness, foreign body sensation, photophobia, tearing, and discharge. Epithelial irregularities, epithelial or subepithelial infiltrates, and pseudodendrites could be observed. Later signs include stromal infiltrates (ring-shaped, disciform, or numular), satellite lesions, epithelial defects, radial keratoneuritis, scleritis, and anterior uveitis (with possible hypopyon). Advanced signs include stromal thinning and corneal perforation (Bang *et al.*, 2010).

iii- Bacterial corneal ulcer:

Bacterial corneal ulcer is an infective keratitis caused by different types of bacteria, and can be investigated as follows:

Central localized ulcer associated with hypopyon, and non edematous clear stroma. For progressive ulcers, severe perforation, and anterior chamber reaction (hypopyon formation) may appear (Pavan, 1994).

iv- Mycotic corneal ulcer:

Mycotic corneal ulcer is an infective keratitis caused by different types of fungi. Fungal infection may be superficial within the collagen-bound lamellae of the mediate stromal tissue of human cornea. However, it may invade deeper areas,

and reach the anterior chamber of the human eye in rare cases of aggressive fungal growth (Sandhu, and Rattan, 1981).

Incidence of different microbial corneal ulcers:

Some representative patient eyes were clinically investigated for severe complications, and proved to have diagnosed infectious ulcers; for which microbial infections were photographed by instant camera (Sony cybershot-DCR-480, Japan) at magnification of 10X.

Microbial isolation and culture techniques:

All samples were collected by flamed "Kummra" platinum spatula (Alcon-Couvreur, Belgium) for hard tissues or by Ethylene gas-sterilized single use cotton swab (BioMed, China) for soft ulcers to avoid perforation. For sensitive patients with increased pain, and hyper-reaction, anesthesia was used as a topical eye drop (Boxinate, Alex. Pharma, Egypt); which was tested for non-antimicrobial activity.

Aseptic conditions of sampling were considered by: firstly avoiding conjunctiva, and eye lids during corneal scraping; secondly Betadine (Nile Pharma, Cairo, Egypt.) was applied as a gentle washing around infected eyes; also samples were isolated in a closed controlled room in the hospital laboratory. Then C-streaks were made on culture plates to distinguish microbial growth coming from corneal scraping, and other plate contaminants (Margo, and Brinser, 1987).

Each sample was cultured on 2 sterile Petri dishes, the first had sterile Sabouraud's dextrose agar (SDA) medium. Chloramphenicol was added to SDA with concentration of 0.05% to avoid bacterial growth for more specific, and selective isolation of fungi. All plates were incubated at 27°C for 4 to 21 days. Fungal colonies were sub cultured for purification, and identification on the same medium under the same incubation conditions. The second plate possessed blood agar and incubated at 37°C to collect bacterial pathogens successfully.

Antimicrobial susceptibility test:

Fungal and bacterial isolates undergone susceptibility tests against the commercially available antibacterial ophthalmic preparations (Allergan, USA, 200 mg/ml) in addition to antifungal ophthalmic preparations (Jansen-Cilag, Belgium, 150 mg/ml) by Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method described by Bauer *et al.* (1966). Antibacterials included ofloxacin, moxifloxacin, gatifloxacin, tobramycin and ciprofloxacin. For antifungals, ketoconazole, fluconazole, itraconazole, natamycin and voriconazole were used. The most resistant isolates were identified for further work.

Cut plug method recorded by Pridham *et al.* (1956) was employed to determine the antimicrobial activity of the chosen essential oils (CAP Pharm for natural oil extraction, Egypt). These oils were sage, anise, black seed, mustard, wheat germ, marjoram, jojoba, clove, chamomile, ginger, camphor, rosemary, watercress, parsley and gum oils.

Freshly prepared spore suspension of the selected fungal and bacterial isolates (0.5ml of about 10^6 cells/ml) was mixed with 9.5ml of melting sterile Sabouraud's dextrose medium (for fungi) or nutrient agar medium (for bacteria) at 45°C, poured on sterile Petri dishes, and left to solidify at room temperature. Regular wells were made in the inoculated agar plates by a sterile cork borer of 0.7 mm diameter. Each well was filled with 0.1 ml of each tested oil. Three replicas were made for each test, and all plates were incubated at 27°C for 3 days for fungi, and at 37°C for 24 hours for bacteria. Then the average diameters of inhibition zones were recorded in centimeters, and compared for all plates.

Identification of fungal and bacterial isolates:

The selected fungal isolates were morphologically, and microscopically examined to be identified according to the following references: Raper and Fennel (1965); and Moubasher (1993). The selected bacterial isolates were identified morphologically and biochemically according to VITEK 2C (Biomérieux, France) then the results were interpreted by using VITEK software (version 06.01).

Determination of minimum inhibitory concentrations of the selected essential oils:

The MIC of the tested essential oils was determined separately according to a modified procedure from Peng *et al.* (2010). The essential oil was serially diluted with dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) to obtain decreasing concentrations in the range of 100, 80, 60, 40, 20, 0.0% v/v. A mixture of 0.5 ml of each concentration and 9.5 ml of molten agar of the appropriate nutrition medium (Sabouraud's dextrose agar for fungi and Mueller Hinton agar for bacteria) was settled in sterile Petri plates; than each plate was inoculated with 10 μ L of standardized inoculum (10^6 cfu/ml) of the tested microorganisms separately, incubated at 27°C for 48 h. for *Aspergillus niger* and at 37°C for 24 h. for *Staphylococcus aureus*. The MIC was defined as the lowest concentration of oil at which no visible growth was observed. The experiment was performed in triplicates.

Transmission electron microscopy for the affected microbial cells:

The selected fungal and bacterial isolates were incubated overnight under proper conditions with MIC of oils of the most promising antimicrobial activity. Each collected cell pellet was fixed by adding 1 ml of 2.5 % glutaraldehyde, and cooled at 4 °C for 2 hrs. Fixed samples were washed with 1% osmic acid for 30 min, washed 3 times with phosphate buffer (pH 7) for 10 min. The samples were dehydrated in ascending ethanol concentrations and then infiltrated with acetone for 1 h. For TEM analysis, samples were embedded in araldite 502 resin to build a plastic mold, that were cut into semi-thin sections in the ultra-cut microtome (LEICA ultracut UCT, Japan), stained with 1% toluidine blue, then ultra-thin sections were prepared, stained with uranyl acetate, and counter stained with lead citrate (Ardenne and Beischer, 1940). Full-stained ultra-thin sections were examined using the transmission electron microscope (JEOL-JEM-100SX, Japan) with beam current 60 μ A, and high voltage of 80 KV.

Histopathological examinations of mice corneal tissues, treated with the selected oils:

Histopathological examination was carried out for healthy mice's corneal tissues to approve safety of the selected oils to be applied topically on the eyes according to the procedure of Gurr (1956) as follows:

Selection and treatment of experimental animals:

Three albino mice of 2 weeks age, and 30 g weight were adapted for laboratory conditions in separate special cages for 3days before work.

The selected oils were prepared in the form of topical eye drops by suspending their MIC in sterile distilled water, containing 0.01% cetrimide as an emulsifying agent to avoid the side effects of other irritating organic solvents (Klotz *et al.*, 2000).

A volume of 0.2 ml of each oil MIC was topically dropped into the right eye of each mouse. Left eyes of all mice were left untreated. Other mice groups were treated with standard topical eye drops (commercial itraconazole as an antifungal agent and gatifloxacin as an antibacterial agent). All treatments were applied every 3 hours for a day (referred to manufacturer recommendation). All treatments were performed in triplicate.

Separation of intact corneal tissues:

Mice were sacrificed after 2 hours of the last dose (without using anaesthesia). Alcoholic Bouin fixative solution was prepared by mixing 150ml of 80% ethanol+ 60ml of 40% formalin+ 15ml of glacial acetic acid+ 1gm of picric acid crystals. The fixative solution (0.1ml) was injected in the anterior chamber of the eye by 27 gauge needle (MASCO, Egypt) in order to maintain the intact of endothelium. Another 0.1ml of fixative solution was dropped on the eye surface (to maintain the intact of epithelium of cornea).

Treated, and control corneas were excised from dissected eyes under aseptic conditions with a rim of sclera by making 360° incision, just behind the limbus, using sterile Alcon short cut pointed surgical blade (size no.:11) in order to avoid corneal injury.

Excised corneal samples were immediately soaked in the alcoholic Bouin fixative solution, and let for 24 hours.

Preparation of corneal sections:

Excess fixative components were removed by washing corneal samples with distilled water for 5 minutes, and then dehydrated by soaking in serial dilutions of ethanol (30, 50, 70, 80% respectively). Colourless corneas were soaked for 5 minutes in 95% ethanol with traces of eosin dye to be distinguished during the next preparation of paraffin blocks, then clarified by soaking in xylene for 5 minutes (miscible with paraffin) to avoid turbidity of ethanol (immiscible

with paraffin). Corneal samples were transferred into molten soft paraffin bath, left for 2 hours to allow paraffin to infiltrate the corneal tissues effectively. Then paraffin blocks were solidified by immersing in cold water immediately.

Sections of 5 μ m thickness were made from paraffin blocks containing corneal samples by rotary microtome with clean sharp heated biconcave knife (Alcon-Couvreur, Belgium). Sections were floated on clean microscopic glass slides with 0.2% albumin fixative, heated on water vapour at 40°C to be spread on the slides by a clean spatula. Desired sections were adhered to slides by gelatin-blood serum mixture. Paraffin was completely dissolved by toluene, and dried by hot air dryer, and then adhered sections were soaked with absolute ethanol for 2 minutes.

Staining and light microscopy of corneal sections:

Principle dye was hematoxylin; hematoxylin solution is composed of 2gm hematoxylin + 100ml methanol + 100ml glycerol + 3gm ammonia alum + 100ml distilled water + 0.24g Na-iodate. Counter dye is eosin; eosin solution is composed of 1gm eosin Y [C.I.45380], 5ml glacial acetic acid, and completed to 1000ml of 70% ethanol.

Deparaffinized slides were stained for 20 minutes with hematoxylin solution. Then slides were washed for 5 minutes with distilled water, destained by 0.5% HCl in 70% ethanol. Ammonia was added dropwise till nuclei come dark against colourless background. Slides were dehydrated in 70% ethanol. Dehydrated slides were counter stained for 5 minutes with eosin solution. Excess stain was removed. Slides were dehydrated by serial ethanol dilutions. Clearing of sections was obtained by xylene till visible red tissues with brownish nuclei were observed. Stained sections were permanently mounted by soaking with aqueous Hoyer mounting medium (30gm gum Arabic + 200gm chloral hydrate + 16ml glycerol + 50ml distilled water). A glass cover was stucked, and left warm overnight.

Slides of corneal sections were examined, using light microscope (Celestron, PentaView, USA) with critical illumination of 1500 lux lamp, substage condensing lens, and iris diaphragm. Light was centered, 10X ocular, and 40X objective lenses were focused on the specimens to be examined. Sharp images were photographed with magnification power of 400X by Celestron built in digital camera.

FT-IR analysis of the selected essential oils:

The FT-IR spectrum of the selected essential oils (chamomile and rosemary) was obtained separately using Bruker-Tensor-27-FT-IR spectrometer (Germany) at the Tanta University Central Lab. Functional groups were determined with the help of IR correlation charts. The IR spectra were reported in % transmittance and represented graphically as a relation between % transmittance versus wavenumber (cm^{-1}). The wave number region for analysis was 5000-200

cm⁻¹. Essential oil samples were prepared by compression of one oil drop between two transparent KBr discs.

Results and Discussion

Cultures of corneal superficial swabs and deep scrapings were taken from 112 ulcer patients, previously treated empirically without the benefit of microbiological data. Out of the collected samples, clinical examination of ophthalmologists revealed that 37 patients possessed viral or acanthamoebal infections (Photo 1), that were confirmed by the absence of bacterial and fungal growth on the incubated plates.

Microbial culture findings yielded pure fungal growth in 38.7%, pure bacterial growth in 42.7% and mixed fungal and bacterial growth in 18.6% out of the 75 cases of positive culture findings (Figure 1).

Microbiological studies depending on the culture of corneal ulcers are the gold standard for determining the etiology of infectious keratitis due to bacteria or fungi. The rationale for empirical treatment is based upon the assumption that a majority of cases of microbial infections will respond to modern broad spectrum antibiotics. However, it is acknowledged that the success of such empirical therapy rests upon the ability of the clinicians to identify through clinical history, signs and symptoms the non-bacterial organisms such as fungi, *Acanthamoeba* and viruses (Shah *et al.*, 2010).

Severity of the resistant fungal and bacterial ulcers referred to the development of many complications, that could be non-curable in late stages of ulcers, which were non-responding to conventional treatments. Prolonged duration of microbial growth within the corneal tissue may cause severe endophthalmitis with inflammations and lysis of internal eye tissues (Photo 2a), or corneal perforation at different sites (Photo 2b). A representative complication in Photo (2c) showed corneal facet with ulcerative thinning and erosion of corneal layers. Melting of corneal layers, loosening of collagen lamellae and epithelial layers was observed in Photo (2d). Common appearance of resistant ulcers was the corneal opacity with white scarring of microbial growth (Photo 2e). In Addition, active keratitis with eye hypersensitivity, redness and excessive tear secretion was revealed in Photo (2f). These complications could easily cause blindness and even eye excision; following the failed treatments of fungal and bacterial keratitis.

Other complications associated with mixed fungal and bacterial infections of the human cornea showed the following symptoms: localized peripheral ulcer with mild corneal thinning, dense hypopyon surrounding the microbial growth within the corneal tissues, multi localized lesions of low population of microbial growth, active keratitis due to a dense central microbial growth and dominant corneal scarring with dense precipitates of microbial elements and secretions. Culture findings in the present survey revealed the mixed microbial growth as a common contamination source for corneal infections of contact lens users, as illustrated in Photo (3).

These recorded complications were in agreement with many epidemiological studies, showing that there was an increased incidence of corneal ulceration among soft contact lens wearers (Jeng *et al.*, 2010). Physiologically, fungal and bacterial

infections can be established due to the high capacity of different microbial elements for adhesion to the host cells, and aided by fungal enzymes production, such as lipase and collagenase, for destroying the host anatomical defense mechanisms, and host surface barriers. Adhesion of microbial elements to the corneal surface depends on both host, and pathogen factors, beside the surrounding circumstances. Firstly, host factors include tears viscosity due to their lipid content, and minor injuries resulting from dust, or contact lens frictions; facilitating the attraction of microbial elements to the corneal surface, then their penetration into injured corneal layers. On the other hand, microbial infections can be predisposed by prolonged antibiotic treatment, or corticosteroid overdoses, leading to immunocompromised corneal surface, more susceptible for microbial infections. Pathogen factors improving adhesion of microbial elements to corneal surface, include the rough surface of air-borne spores of filamentous fungi as a distinct morphological character, and some slimy lipid secretions on the surface of pathogenic unicellular forms (Martin, *et al.*, 1995).

The antimicrobial agents available today are mostly microbistatic, requiring a prolonged course of therapy. The antimicrobial activity of fluconazole, itraconazole, voriconazole, ketoconazole and natamycin against fungal isolates and ofloxacin, moxifloxacin, gatifloxacin, tobramycin and ciprofloxacin against bacterial isolates illustrated their capacities to inhibit the growth of microbial isolates, that were quite resistant to ketoconazole, natamycin, tobramycin and ciprofloxacin as indicated in Figures (2 and 3). The antifungal activity of itraconazole revealed that it is the drug of choice in the present culture sensitivity findings. The largest and most widely used class of antifungal agents is that of the azole derivatives. All inhibit ergosterol biosynthesis pathway in fungal metabolism (Moon *et al.*, 2014). Antibacterial activity of gatifloxacin, moxifloxacin and ofloxacin were found to be nearly similar with potential activity against tested bacterial isolates from corneal ulcers. These second and third generation fluoroquinolones are registered for the treatment of bacterial corneal infections, that were caused by *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus* and *Corynebacterium* species. They are also effective in treating more severe cases of bacterial keratitis (David *et al.*, 2011).

As shown in Table (1), the resistance of tested fungal and bacterial isolates against the selected commercial antimicrobial agents (5 agents or each of fungi and bacteria) showed a high frequency of multiple drug resistance and up to 80% resistance was obtained for 2 fungal isolates and 3 bacterial isolates, which were selected for further detailed study.

Microbial keratitis can progress rapidly and generally requires urgent antifungal and antibacterial therapy to eliminate the pathogen. With a growing incidence of infections resistant to synthetic antimicrobials, an arsenal of new generations of antimicrobial agents is needed. Natural products from plants could be interesting alternatives (George *et al.*, 2008). In the recent years, there has been an increasing interest in the use of natural substances and some questions concerning the safety of synthetic compounds have encouraged more detailed studies of more plant resources such as essential oils, which have been searched for their antibacterial,

antifungal, antiviral, insecticidal, anticancer and antioxidant properties (Sivamani *et al.*, 2014).

In agar well diffusion method, the selected highly resistant 2 fungal isolates and 3 bacterial isolates were tested against 15 commercial essential oils (sage, anise, black seed, mustard, wheat germ, marjoram, jojoba, clove, chamomile, ginger, camphor, rosemary, watercress, parsley and gum oils). Chamomile and rosemary were the most potent essential oils against the selected fungal and bacterial isolates, respectively (Figures 4 and 5).

According to culture and microscopic examinations, both fungal isolates of interest were found belonging to *Aspergillus niger*. Conventional morphological and biochemical tests of the 3 recovered bacterial isolates revealed that these isolates were *Staphylococcus aureus*, which was confirmed by VITEK 2C test.

The safety of the most potent essential oils in the present survey was determined through FT-IR analysis, as shown in Figures (6 and 7) and Tables (2 and 3). In the FT-IR spectrum of chamomile and rosemary oils, the wave number range of 2000-2250 cm^{-1} showed the absence of toxic cyano ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) group and acetylenic group ($\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$). The selected essential oils were characterized by the presence of aldehyde groups ($-\text{CHO}$) within the wave number range of 2850-2900 cm^{-1} , while the wave number range of 1700-1750 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of aliphatic unsaturated hydrocarbon double bonds ($\text{C}=\text{C}$), all were represented with strong peaks.

Rosemary and chamomile essential oils were the most effective as antibacterial and antifungal agents, respectively. Their activities have been attributed to the presence of some active functional groups. Sensitivity of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Aspergillus niger* to the tested oils were in line with many earlier studies (Oussalah *et al.*, 2006; Kaur and Arora, 2009; Panahi *et al.*, 2011; and Teixeira *et al.*, 2012).

Santoyo *et al.* (2005) investigated the antimicrobial activity of rosemary essential oil against *S. aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*. *S. aureus* was found to be the most sensitive bacteria. The single membrane of G+ve bacteria is considerably more susceptible to permeation by antimicrobials (Wen *et al.*, 2003). In the same manner, Tolouee *et al.* (2010) and Hadi *et al.* (2013) recorded the antifungal activity of high concentrations of chamomile essential oil against *Aspergillus niger*. The chamomile oil showed antimicrobial activity against certain species of bacteria, fungi and viruses in vitro (Lis-Balchin *et al.*, 1998). The chamomile oil was effective against *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium culmorum* and *Fusarium moniliforme* (Soliman and Badaea, 2002).

MIC of chamomile and rosemary oils and cfu counts showed potent antimicrobial activity of chamomile at 60% (v/v) against *Aspergillus niger* and of rosemary at 40% (v/v) against *Staphylococcus aureus*, as revealed in Table (4).

The knowledge of both the mode and mechanism of action of essential oils is crucial to ensure their usefulness in therapeutic practice (Lahlou, 2004), while essential oils have been extensively screened for their antifungal activity, interaction between the oils and microorganisms, which is lately responsible for, is poorly

understood. Regarding the few studies of this matter, *Aspergillus sp.* and *Candida sp.* have been the species mostly used (Pinto *et al.*, 2009).

Transmission electron microscopy was used to detect the ultrastructure changes of *Aspergillus niger* in the presence of chamomile oil (MIC = 60% v/v). Photo (4) illustrated the lysis of spore and hyphal walls, disintegration of mitochondria, endoplasmic reticulum and other cellular organelles. In addition, agglutination of cytoplasmic proteins and leakage of soluble cell contents could be observed, comparing with intact non-treated spores and hyphae. These findings were similar to other investigations (Tavares *et al.*, 2010; Zuzarte *et al.*, 2011; and Tolouee *et al.*, 2010).

Transmission electron micrographs of *Staphylococcus aureus* treated with rosemary oil are represented in Photo (5). *Staphylococcus aureus* under study (without treatment) has a typical structure of G+ve cocci and the cells show a regular wall. Generally, after the bacterial cells were exposed to rosemary (MIC = 40% v/v), there were several changes, included significant shrinking and reduction of cell size. In addition, severe destruction of outer cell shape, cell wall dissolving with less cell content leakage and intracellular protein agglutinations. It might be proposed that in the primary phase, the tested essential oil bind to the cell surface and penetrate into the cell wall, causing it to swell, followed by cytoplasmic membrane damage, while the cells shrink as a defense against the tested oil, as reviewed by Burt (2004). The antibacterial action of essential oils has been reviewed by Aiemsaard *et al.* (2011), recording that transmission electron micrographs demonstrated morphological changes of *Staphylococcus aureus* DMST 4745, showing leakage of cell constituents and the cell contents of many bacterial cells were lost.

For more confirmation of safe use of the investigated essential oils to be topically used as antimicrobial agents for treatment of fungal and bacterial infections of the cornea, histological examinations of mice cornea were obtained after their treatment with the selected essential oils comparing with commercial antimicrobial ophthalmic preparations and healthy non-treated control mice cornea. Healthy cornea possessed normal arrangement and size of epithelium, endothelium, stroma and normal bound collagen lamellae. Both chamomile and rosemary showed nearly similar size of corneal layers with mild rare infiltrates within collagen lamellae, comparing non-treated cornea. On the other hand, itraconazole as a standard antifungal agent gave severe infiltration and losing of collagen lamellae, while gatifloxacin as a standard antibacterial agent gave less damaging effect and mild corneal infiltrates. This comparison encouraged the safe usage of chamomile and rosemary on corneal tissues with normal layers arrangement, size and absence of any toxic precipitates, with only rare corneal infiltrates, that can be normally regenerated at the end of treatment of corneal ulcer (Photo 6).

Figure 1: Incidence of different microbial findings among the investigated resistant corneal ulcers.

Photo 1: Representative symptoms of the different types of infectious corneal ulcers, depending on clinical findings.

Photo 2: Representative examples for the different complications associated with fungal and bacterial infections of the human cornea, confirmed by culture findings.

- a: endophthalmitis, b: corneal perforation, c: corneal facet,
d: corneal melting, e: corneal opacity, f: active keratitis.**

Photo 2: continued.

<p>Localized peripheral ulcer with mild corneal thinning.</p>	<p>Dispersed microbial growth with dense hypopyon within corneal tissue.</p>
<p>Multipolar peripheral ulcers with faint microbial growth.</p>	<p>Central corneal ulcer with active sensation.</p>
<p>Contact lens-associated ulcer with mixed fungal and bacterial infection</p>	
<p>Corneal scarring with dense microbial growth and mild corneal melting.</p>	<p>Mixed microbial growth of a contaminated contact lens, used by a female student</p>

Photo 3: Representative examples for the different complications associated with mixed fungal and bacterial infections of the human cornea, confirmed by culture findings.

Figure 2: Incidence of resistance of fungal isolates against some commercially available antifungal ophthalmic preparations.

Figure 3: Incidence of resistance of bacterial isolates against some commercially available antibacterial ophthalmic preparations.

Table 1: Percentage of resistance against antimicrobial ophthalmic preparations among the isolated fungal and bacterial populations:

Percentage of antimicrobial resistance	No. of fungal isolates	No. of bacterial isolates
0.0%	0.0	0.0
20%	4	2
40%	9	10
60%	28	31
80%	2	3
100%	0.0	0.0

Figure 4: Sensitivity of the most resistant fungal isolates against some selected essential oils.

Figure 5: Sensitivity of the most resistant bacterial isolates against some selected essential oils.

Figure 6: FT-IR analysis of chamomile oil.

Table 2: Functional group profile of chamomile oil by FT-IR analysis:

Functional group	Range of wave number (cm ⁻¹)	Presence in chamomile oil
Hydroxyl group (OH)	3300-3500	Absent
Amino group (NH ₂)	3200-3400	Absent
Aliphatic saturated hydrocarbon chains (CH ₃ , CH ₂ , CH)	2850-2980	Present
Aldehyde group (CHO)	2850-2900	Present
Carbonyl group (-C=O)	1700-1750	Present
Aliphatic unsaturated hydrocarbon double bonds (-C=C-)	1500-1600	Present
Aromatic hydrocarbon ring	3100-3200	Absent
Cyano group (C≡N)	2000-2250	Absent
Acetylenic group (C≡C)	2000-2250	Absent

Figure 7: FT-IR analysis of rosemary oil.

Table 3: Functional group profile of rosemary oil by FT-IR analysis:

Functional group	Range of wave number (cm ⁻¹)	Presence in rosemary oil
Hydroxyl group (OH)	3300-3500	Present
Amino group(NH ₂)	3200-3400	Present
Aliphatic saturated hydrocarbon chains (CH ₃ , CH ₂ , CH)	2850-2980	Present
Aldehyde group (CHO)	2850-2900	Present
Carbonyl group(-C=O)	1700-1750	Present
Aliphatic unsaturated hydrocarbon double bonds (-C=C-)	1500-1600	Present
Aromatic hydrocarbon ring	3100-3200	Absent
Cyano group (C≡N)	2000-2250	Absent
Acetylenic group (C≡C)	2000-2250	Absent

Table 4: MIC of essential oils against the selected fungal and bacterial isolates:

Concentration of essential oil (% v/v)	Microbial growth (cfu/ml)	
	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> versus chamomile	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> versus rosemary
0.0 (Control DMSO)	10 ⁶	10 ⁶
20	2.4x10 ³	1.3x10 ²
40	0.8x10 ²	0.0
60	0.0	0.0
80	0.0	0.0
100	0.0	0.0

Photo 4: Transmission electron micrograph of *Aspergillus niger* growth elements, treated with chamomile oil, compared with control at 5000X.

A: control spores, B: control hyphae, C and D: treated spores, E and F: treated hyphae.

Photo 5: Transmission electron micrograph of *Staphylococcus aureus* vegetative cells, treated with rosemary oil, compared with control at 20000X.

A: control bacterial cells, B, C, D, E and F: treated bacterial cells.

Photo 6: Histological effects of the selected essential oils on the mice corneal tissues.

- A: Non-treated mouse cornea.
- B: Mouse cornea treated with chamomile oil.
- C: Mouse cornea treated with itraconazole.
- D: Mouse cornea treated with rosemary oil.
- E: Mouse cornea treated with gatifloxacin.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Highly observable ratio of fungal and bacterial isolates from human keratitis was reported to be resistant to prescribed antimicrobials, followed by severe complication. Particularly, the investigated *Aspergillus niger* and *Staphylococcus aureus* possessed resistance against 80% of the tested commercial antimicrobial agents.

With regard to the antimicrobial activity of chamomile and rosemary oils under investigation, comparing with commercially used antimicrobials for ophthalmic infections, these essential oils could be used as antifungal and antibacterial agents of natural origin.

FT-IR analysis revealed the absence of toxic cyano and acetylenic groups in both chamomile and rosemary essential oils.

Further investigations of oil composition, characterization of ingredients responsible for oil antimicrobial activity and histological studies for the prolonged treatment of the target corneal tissues with the selected essential oils.

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الملخص العربي

الزيوت العطرية: علاج واعد ضد التهابات قرنية الإنسان الفطرية والبكتيرية.

أنور سعيد محمد البدرى، سامح سمير على.

قسم النبات، كلية العلوم، جامعة طنطا.

المراسلة: سامح سمير على- قسم النبات- كلية العلوم- جامعة طنطا.

من بين 112 قرحة قرنية، والتي تم تشخيصها سريريا كمرضى بالعدوى الميكروبية (فطرية، بكتيرية، شوك أميبية وفيروسية)، من المترددين على العيادة الخارجية والقسم الداخلى لطب وجراحة العين بمستشفيات جامعة طنطا، فى غضون 6 أشهر (أبريل- ستمبر 2014)؛ تم الكشف عن 43 حالة للعدوى الفطرية، كما ظهرت العدوى البكتيرية فى 46 حالة وفقاً لنتائج المزارع الميكروبية. تم إختبار جميع الفطريات والبكتيريا المعزولة ضد مستحضرات العيون المضادة للميكروبات المتاحة تجارياً (أوفلوكساسين، موكسيفلوكساسين، جاتيفلوكساسين، توبراميسين، سيبروفلوكساسين، للبيكتيريا؛ الكيتوكونازول، الإيتراكونازول، الناتاميسين و الفوريكونازول للفطريات)؛ ومن هذه العزلات وجدت عزلتان إكتسبتا مقاومة 80% ضد مضادات الفطريات، وأعطت 3 عزلات بكتيرية 80% مقاومة للمضادات الحيوية. تم إختبار كل الـ 5 عزلات مقابل 15 من الزيوت العطرية التجارية (زيوت الميرمية، الينسون، الحبة السوداء، الخردل، جنين القمح، البردقوش، الجوجوبا، القرنفل، البابونج، الزنجبيل، الكافور، حصالبان، الجرجير، البقدونس، واللبن). فى حالة العزلات الفطرية، كان زيت البابونج الأكثر فعالية ضد الأسبيرجيللاس نايجر. وسجلت أكبر منطقة تثبيط لعزلات البكتيريا، التى تم تعريفها فى وقت لاحق كـ ستافيلوكوكاس إيرياس، ضد زيت حصالبان. وكان مفعول مضادات الميكروبات من الزيوت المختارة ملحوظاً للغاية وتم إثباته باستخدام الميكروسكوب الإلكتروني النافذ لعناصر النمو لكل من الأسبيرجيللاس نايجر وستافيلوكوكاس إيرياس. وكشفت دراسات فحص الأنسجة على قرنية حيوانات التجارب أن الزيوت المختارة يمكن استخدامها بصورة واعدة فى علاج التهاب القرنية الميكروبية المقاومة.